

The Junia Case, Once Again.

A Response to Esther Yue L. Ng, “Was Junia(s) in Rom 16:7 a Female Apostle? And so What?” (*JETS* 63/3 [2020]: 517-533)

Abstract

In 2020, Esther Yue L. Ng published an article that aimed at reopening the “Junia(s) case” of Romans 16.7. In her article, entitled “Was Junia(s) in Rom 16:7 a Female Apostle? And so What?” (*Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society* 63/3), she challenged the consensus of 21st-century scholarship that the person named IOYNIAN in Rom 16.7 was a woman apostle active in the first diffusion of the Gospel. As Matt H. Hamilton noticed in a review of recent scholarship over Junia, the article by Ng represents so far the most well-written and most challenging production of the 21st-century “anti-Junia” trend. So it is the aim of the current essay to provide a detailed response to it. Going through the three lines of argument mobilised by Ng (Junias could be the Greek rendering of the Hebrew masculine name Yehunni; Junia(s) was perhaps only “well-known to the apostles” instead of being an apostle on her or his own; if a woman apostle, Junia did not have the same responsibilities as male apostles), this essay highlights many methodological shortcomings that run throughout her article. It also unveils the rhetoric of doubt used by Ng, which is manifest particularly in the “funnel” *dispositio* she employs. Finally, this essay exposes the “axiom of unsuspection” that Ng adopts with regard to the issue of androcentrism and her particularly unsatisfactory treatment of how and why the masculine reading Junias had made its mark in modern scholarship and translations.

Keywords

Junia

Romans 16.7

women in early Christianity

androcentrism

textual criticism

history of interpretation

Short Biographical Note on the Author

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Introduction

ἀσπάσασθε Ἀνδρόνικον (Andronicus) καὶ Ἰουνίαν (Junia) τοὺς συγγενεῖς μου καὶ συναιχμαλώτους μου, οἵτινες εἰσιν ἐπίσημοι ἐν τοῖς ἀποστόλοις, οἳ καὶ πρὸ ἐμοῦ γέγοναν ἐν Χριστῷ (Rom 16.7)¹

For the most part of the history of interpretation, the name IOYNIAN that appears in Romans 16:7 has been understood as a feminine name, Ἰουνία (Greek equivalent to the common Latin name *Iunia*). However, a debate arose among modern scholarship as to whether the name should perhaps better be taken as a masculine, *Junias* (Ἰουνιᾶς, with an accent on the alpha). Both of the options technically work with the –ν ending of the accusative. From the 19th century onwards, the masculine interpretation found more and more supporters, eventually becoming the subject of a consensus. Thus, during the 20th century, the reading “Junias” reigned almost unchallenged in commentaries and translations. At the time, it even found its authoritative support in the best grammars and dictionaries of NT Greek (such as Blass-Debrunner’s *Grammatik des neutestamentlichen Griechisch*,² since its first publication in 1896, or Bauer-Danker’s *Griechisch-Deutsches Wörterbuch zu den Schriften des Neuen Testaments*,³ from its first publication in 1928), as well as in the most-reputed critical editions (thus the Nestle-Aland, from 1927 up to 1997, and the UBS, from 1966 up to 1997, both printed Ἰουνιᾶν in Rom 16.7, with the accent on the alpha, with orients towards a masculine reading).⁴

¹ Greek text according to the Nestle-Aland 28th edition. The text-critical issues include (1) the alternative form IOYLIAN (*Julia*) found notably in \mathfrak{P}^{46} 6. 606. 1718. 2685 ar b vg^{mss} bo; (2) the presence of τοὺς before συναιχμαλώτους μου in \mathfrak{P}^{46} and B; (3) various word orders and formulations for the clause οἳ καὶ πρὸ ἐμοῦ γέγοναν ἐν Χριστῷ. The reading *Julia* arguably appeared under the influence of *Julia* a few lines after (cf. Rom 16:15).

² F. Blass, *Grammatik des neutestamentlichen Griechisch* (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht 1896), 71, §29; cf. the English translation of 1961 (*A Greek Grammar of the New Testament and Other Early Christian Literature* [transl. R. W. Funk; Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1961], 86, §125 (2)).

³ For the *Junias* entry, see for example the 5th edition: W. Bauer, *Griechisch-Deutsches Wörterbuch zu den Schriften des Neuen Testaments und der übrigen urchristlichen Literatur* (Berlin: Alfred Töpelmann 1958), 751.

⁴ That the choice of accentuation in NA and UBS is directly linked with the masculine/feminine debate can be seen in B. Metzger, *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament: Second Edition: A Companion Volume to the United Bible Societies’ Greek New Testament (Fourth Revised Edition)* (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft 1994), 475-76.

The reign of the masculine reading was finally put to an end at the turn of the 21st century, after scholars such as Bernadette Brooten (1977), Valentin Fàbrega (1984/85), Peter Lampe (1985 and 2003), Ray R. Schulz (1986-87), Peter Artz (1993), Joseph A. Fitzmyer (1993), Richard Cervin (1994), John Thorley (1996), Uwe-Karsten Plisch (1996), Richard Bauckham (2002), Linda Belleville (2005), and Eldon Epp (2002 and 2005) – to mention only the major names – observed that the gender-name debate over Junia/Junias finds no ground in the ancient sources.⁵ Concretely, the ancient sources unanimously plead for the feminine, be it the Church Fathers,⁶ the early translations into Latin, Coptic, and Syriac,⁷ the accented Greek manuscripts (which *all* have the accent on the iota!),⁸ or, last but not least, the absence of *any* attestation of the masculine name Junias in Antiquity, compared with the numerous ancient attestations of the feminine Junia (especially in ancient Rome,

⁵ B. Brooten, “Junia ... Outstanding Among the Apostles” (Romans 16:7),” in: Leonard Swidler and Arlene Swidler (eds.), *Women Priests: A Catholic Commentary on the Vatican Declaration* (New York: Paulist 1977) 141-44; V. Fàbrega, “War Junia(s), der hervorragende Apostel (Rom 16,7), eine Frau?,” in: *JAC* 27-28 (1984-1985), 47-64; P. Arzt, “Iunia oder Iunias? Zum textkritischen Hintergrund von Röm 16,7,” in: F. V. Reiterer and P. E. Osb (eds.), *Liebe zum Wort: Festschrift für P. Ludger Bernhard Osb* (Salzburg/Wien: Otto Müller Verlag 1993), 83-102; P. Lampe, “Iunia/Iunias: Sklavenherkunft im Kreise der vorpaulinischen Apostel (Röm 16:7),” in: *ZNW* 76 (1985), 132-34; cf. P. Lampe, “The Roman Christians of Romans 16,” in: K.P. Donfried (ed.), *The Romans Debate* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic 1991), 216-230, here 222-24; R. R. Schulz, “Romans 16:7: Junia or Junias?,” in: *ExpTim* 98 (1986-87), 108-10; J.A. Fitzmyer, *Romans: A New Translation and Commentary* (New York: Doubleday 1993), 737-40; R.S. Cervin, “A Note Regarding the Name ‘Junia(s)’ in Romans 16.7,” in: *NTS* 40/3 (1994), 464-70; J. Thorley, “Junia, a Woman Apostle,” in: *NovT* 38:1 (1996), 18-29; U.-K. Plisch, “Die Apostelin Junia: Das exegetische Problem in Röm 16.7 im Licht von Nestle-Aland²⁷ und der sahidischen Überlieferung,” in: *NTS* 42/3 (1996), 477-78; R. Bauckham, *Gospel Women: Studies of the Named Women in the Gospels* (London: T&T Clark 2002), 172-78; L. Belleville, “Ἰουνίαν ... ἐπίσημοι ἐν τοῖς ἀποστόλοις: A Re-examination of Romans 16.7 in Light of Primary Source Materials,” in: *NTS* 51/2 (2005), 231-49; E. J. Epp, “Text-Critical, Exegetical, and Socio-Cultural Factors Affecting the Junia/Junias Variation in Romans 16,7,” in: Aldebert Denaux (ed.), *New Testament Textual Criticism and Exegesis: Festschrift J. Delobel* (Leuven: Peeters 2002), 227-91; cf. E. J. Epp, *Junia: The First Woman Apostle* (Minneapolis: Augsburg Fortress Press 2005). For a survey of the scholarship on Junia since the publication of the book by Epp, see Y.-J. Lin, “Junia: An Apostle before Paul,” in: *JBL* 139/1 (2020), 191-209, and A. Hartmann, “Junia – A Woman Lost in Translation: The Name IOYNIAN in Romans 16:7 and its History of Interpretation,” in: *Open Theology* 6/1 (2020), 646-60.

⁶ Joseph A. Fitzmyer mentions no less than 16 attestations of the feminine interpretation for the first millennium (Fitzmyer, *Romans: A New Translation with Introduction and Commentary* [New York et al.: Doubleday 1993], 737-38). On the interpretation of Rom 16:7 by early Christian writers, cf. Epp, *Junia*, 32-39.

⁷ See Artz, “Iunia oder Iunias?,” 94-95; Thorley, “Junia, a Woman Apostle,” 20-24. On Sahidic Coptic manuscripts more specifically, see Plisch, “Die Apostelin Junia.”

⁸ Despite what was suggested in the apparatuses of some editions of the NA and UBS up to 1998, we do not possess a single manuscript that would support the reading Ἰουνιᾶν (with the accent on the alpha)! On this, see Artz, “Iunia oder Iunias?,” 87-94; cf. Epp, *Junia*, 49-52.

with over 250 attestations among inscriptions).⁹ Based on these elements, the scholarly consensus returned to the old view that Andronicus' companion in Romans 16:7 is a woman apostle. A decisive step in this direction was taken in 1998, when the Nestle-Aland and the UBS editions modified their accentuation to go back to the feminine spelling Ἰουβίαν.¹⁰

Such a change in the scholarly consensus did not come without resistance, however. From the 2000s onwards, dissenting voices have started to be heard. These voices come mainly from the range of theologians holding a so-called “complementarian” approach to men-women relationships: thus, for example, Wayne Grudem, John Piper, Daniel B. Wallace, Michael H. Burer, Albert M. Wolters, David Huttar, Kevin DeYoung, and Esther Yue L. Ng herself.¹¹ Besides the issue of the gender of Junia(s), these scholars question whether Junia is really called “apostle” in Romans 16:7 and if yes, what this title may have meant for a woman in the mid-first century CE. In her article, entitled “Was Junia(s) in Rom 16:7 a Female Apostle? And so What?” and published in 2020 in the *Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society*, Ng mobilises and articulates these three different lines of argument. I agree with Matt H. Hamilton that this article represents so far the “most challenging” and “most well-written” production of the anti-Junia movement and that “further research on Junia should involve the inclusion of and response to the arguments made by Ng.”¹² To be clear, in my view the article is not that challenging as to the arguments advanced: there is nothing really new and Ng's argumentation is all in all unconvincing, as I shall demonstrate

⁹ Lampe, “The Roman Christians of Romans 16,” 223; cf. Cervin, “A Note Regarding the Name ‘Junia(s),’” 466. Junia was a popular name in Rome due to the presence of the *gens Iunia* (masculine counterpart: *Iunius*).

¹⁰ That this change of accent reflects a change of view on the part of the editors concerning Junia's gender is beyond doubt (for the details of the reasoning, see Epp, *Junia*, 48).

¹¹ W. Grudem and J. Piper, *Recovering Biblical Manhood and Womanhood* (Wheaton: Crossway, 1991); M. H. Burer and D. B. Wallace, “Was Junia Really an Apostle? A Re-examination of Rom 16.7,” in: *NTS* 47/1 (2001), 76-91; W. Grudem, *Evangelical Feminism and Biblical Truth: An Analysis of More than One Hundred Disputed Questions* (Sisters: Multnomah 2004); D. Huttar, “Did Paul Call Andronicus an Apostle in Romans 16:7?,” in: *JETS* 52/4 (2009), 747-78; M. Burer, “ΕΠΙΣΗΜΟΙ ἘΝ ΤΟΙΣ ΑΠΟΣΤΟΛΟΙΣ in Rom 16:7 as ‘Well Known to the Apostles:’ Further Defense and New Evidence,” in: *JETS* 58/4 (2015), 731-55; E.Y.L. Ng, “Was Junia(s) in Rom 16:7 a Female Apostle? And so What?,” *JETS* 63/3 (2020), 517-33 (cf. also, from the same author, “Did Joanna Become Junia?,” *JETS* 65/3 (2022): 523-34); K. DeYoung, *Men and Women in the Church: A Short, Biblical, Practical Introduction* (Wheaton: Crossway, 2021). For a comprehensive review of recent publications (from 2010 up to 2022) that go against the consensus for Junia apostle, see M. H. Hamilton, “Junia as a Female Apostle in Romans 16:7: A Literature Review of Relevant Sources from 2010 to Present 2022,” in: *Eleutheria* 6/1 (2022), 32-77.

¹² M. H. Hamilton, “Junia as a Female Apostle,” here 58.

in the discussion below. However, I would admit that the article is rhetorically powerful in the way it combines and articulates many unconnected arguments to build a rather coherent picture. For that reason, it is worth taking the time to highlight the methodological problems that run throughout Ng's discussion and to counter her argumentation.

The Aim and the Rhetorical Strategy of Ng's Article

The announced aim of Ng's article is to discuss the potential implications of Romans 16:7 for women's ministries in today's churches. "Should the church today follow Paul's precedent and likewise affirm leadership and teaching roles for women equivalent to men?" (p. 518), she asks. In her view, the answer is quite clear: The "growing consensus" in scholarship that "Junia was clearly an apostle in her own right" (p. 517) is deemed "problematic" (p. 518), and thus Rom 16:7 cannot be taken as "a historical precedent to advocate for equal ministry opportunity for women and men" (p. 517). Ng asserts that "alternative interpretations are worthy of consideration and even preferable" (p. 518). Further, she announces that she also wishes to challenge the "charge of androcentrism" that an androcentric bias led Christian leaders and institutions to transform a woman into a man (pp. 517 and 519). This point refers to the explanation first advanced by Bernadette Brooten in 1977 – and now widely accepted in scholarship – that Junia was transformed into Junias because an androcentric bias made some interpreters to believe that a woman apostle is unlikely, if not impossible by definition.¹³ While conceding that a certain anti-women trend might have been at work at some points in the church's history ("this is not to say that the church has never discriminated against women" [p. 532]), Ng makes very clear from the start of her article that she is not convinced by the androcentric-bias line of explanation in the case of the Junia/Junias debate.

Keeping in mind the above permits us to better apprehend the rhetoric of Ng's essay. The strategy consists of casting doubts on different aspects of the debate. In terms of *dispositio*, the author employs what can be called the "funnel technique," made of three steps that each corresponds to a part of the article: (1) In the first part, entitled "Junia(s): Male or Female," Ng suggests that there are still serious doubts in scholarship over the gender of Junia(s) and

¹³ Brooten, "Junia ... Outstanding Among the Apostles."

argues that a masculine interpretation is more likely. (2) In the second part, entitled “Was Junia(s) an Apostle?” (note the presence of the “s” in brackets, which maintains doubts as to the gender), she refers to the Burer-Wallace hypothesis¹⁴ of an exclusive meaning for the expression ἐπίσημοι ἐν τοῖς ἀποστόλοις. So, in substance: Paul perhaps did not call Andronicus and Junia(s) apostles but only designated them as “well-known to the apostles.” (3) In the third part, entitled “The Role of Junia (if Woman) in the First Century” (the specification “if woman” is doing a lot of work here), Ng drives home her point by advancing that even if we admit the very unlikely scenario that Junia was a woman apostle, then her apostolic title should not be taken literally as implying that she worked at equal with men apostles. These three points correspond to the main poles of the 21st-century anti-Junia rhetoric that Matt H. Hamilton identified: (1) the “Name-Gender debate”; (2) the “Syntax-Grammar debate”; (3) the “Apostleship debate.”¹⁵ I will make use of this same terminology below.

Evaluation of Ng’s Three Lines of Argument

The Name-Gender Debate: “Junia(s): Male or Female?” (p. 519-525)

In the first part of her article, which is the longest and most detailed part, Ng considers the *Name-Gender debate*. She carefully avoids repeating the 18th-century (and now abandoned) theory that Junias would be a hypocorism of the Latin name *Iunianus*.¹⁶ Instead, she bases her case on a more recent hypothesis advanced in 2008 by Al Wolters, in an article published in the *Journal of Biblical Literature*.¹⁷ The suggestion is as follows: Ἰουνίας in Romans 16:7 (with the accent on the iota) might reflect the Hebrew name יְהוּנָי (to be vocalised Yēhunnī), of which we have two attestations on ossuaries from Palestine, dating probably between 70 and 135.¹⁸ Wolters posits that יְהוּנָי is itself an abbreviated form

¹⁴ Burer and Wallace, “Was Junia Really an Apostle?”

¹⁵ Hamilton, “Junia as a Female Apostle.” Hamilton identifies a fourth pole, the “Rhetoric-Context Debate,” that Ng mobilises only to a lesser extent in link with the “Syntax-Grammar Debate” (= pp. 526-27 of Ng’s article).

¹⁶ On the history and influence of this theory, see Epp, *Junia*, 40–44. For a critical evaluation based on linguistic grounds, see Thorley, “Junia, a Woman Apostle,” 24–25.

¹⁷ A. L. Wolters, “IOYNIAN (Romans 16:7) and the Hebrew Name Yēhunnī,” in: *Journal of Biblical Literature* 127/2 (2008), 397-408.

¹⁸ See Wolters, “IOYNIAN,” 402.

of the theophoric name יהונייה (Yehunniyah), meaning “May Yahweh be gracious.”¹⁹ He also suggests taking Yehunni to be a masculine name and argues that it would be Hellenized as Ἰουνιάς in Greek, following the first declension masculine.²⁰

Ng deems Wolter’s suggestion highly convincing. She mentions two main arguments to support her appreciation: (a) Andronicus and Junia(s) were “certainly Jews” (given that Paul describes them as his συγγενεῖς in Rom 16.7, i.e., his “relatives”) and so it makes sense to look for a Hebrew name behind IOYNIAN (p. 521-522); (b) Yehunni is an attested Jewish masculine name, in contrast with Junia, which is unattested “for *Jewish women* who lived in the first century” (p. 522 – my italics) and only barely attested for Jewish women during Antiquity (p. 522). Such reasoning suffers from serious methodological problems. To begin with, one can think that Junia(s) was a Jew without necessarily looking for a Hebrew name behind it. If a woman, she may also have taken the Latin name *Iunia*, rather than strictly transliterating or translating her name. But let us admit for a while that a Hebrew name should be looked for. Still, the way Ng contrasts a *Latin feminine name* (*Iunia*) with the *Hebrew masculine name* (Yehunni) is problematic for two reasons. First, because Yehunni is not that clearly a masculine name. As Wolters himself states, Yehunni “could also be a woman’s name”!²¹ Ng’s report does not make this point sufficiently clear. Second, one has to compare only what is comparable: to keep it with Hebrew names, Yehunni is so far attested only twice, while the feminine name Yeohanna (Joanna)²² is well-attested. For instance, for the period 330 BCE-200 CE, Tal Ilan’s *Lexicon of Jewish Names* lists twelve women named Joanna in Palestine out of a total of 402 women, which makes Joanna a popular name.²³ Concretely, this means that not only the Latin name *Iunia* (Ἰουνία in Greek) is well-attested while *Iunias* (Ἰουνιάς in Greek) is not, but also the Hebrew female name Yeohanna/Joanna is far more attested than Yehunni. From this point, if we wish to identify a Hebrew name behind the accusative IOYNIAN in Rom 16.7, why

¹⁹ Wolters, “IOYNIAN,” 400.

²⁰ Wolters, “IOYNIAN,” 398-399.

²¹ See the discussion between Al Wolters and Richard Fellows on the blog of Fellows, <http://paulandco-workers.blogspot.com/2011/02/al-wolters-responds-on-junia.html> (27 August 2023).

²² On the etymology of Joanna, see the recent article by I. Koutchoukali, “The Name Johanna: Some Historical, Etymological, and Cultural Notes,” in: J. Bradley (ed.), *Tonavan Laakso: Eine Festschrift für Johanna Laakso* (Wien: Praesens 2022), 63-65.

²³ T. Ilan, *Lexicon of Jewish Names in Late Antiquity: Part 1: Palestine 330 BCE - 200 CE* (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck 2002), 57.

not also consider Joanna as a candidate? Intriguingly, a Jewish woman called Ἰωάννα is mentioned in the Gospel of Luke as a member of the women group who followed Jesus (Lk 8:3), and later as part of the group of women who first witnessed the empty tomb and announced the resurrection (Lk 24.10). Is this not typically a woman who acted as an apostle? That the Joanna of Luke's Gospel might be the same person as the Junia of Romans 16:7 was suggested by Richard Bauckham in 2002 and later supported, among others, by Ben Witherington (2005) and Constantina A. Clark (2018).²⁴ Surprisingly, Ng does not take the time to discuss this hypothesis. She only mentions it in a footnote and quickly concludes that it is “pleading and unpersuasive” (p. 522, n. 20).²⁵ The last that can be said here is that she omits several pieces of the puzzle.

If we nevertheless wish to follow Wolters and Ng in adopting the Yehunni hypothesis, then we have to face the fact that all the Church Fathers took IOYNIAN to be feminine. Ng takes the time to address this issue. To put all the data in a coherent scenario, she suggests that most of the Church Fathers mistook Junias for Junia for they wrongly “regarded Ἰουνίαν as derived from Latin, and so took it to be a female name” (p. 525). By contrast, Origen, in the third century, and Epiphanius, in the fourth, would not have fallen into this misunderstanding. Specifically, according to Ng's conjecture, Origen and Epiphanius “noted that the Jewish men mentioned in the Greek Bible frequently bore names ending in –ιας, and so they did not take Junia(s) to be a woman” (p. 525). Let us first briefly address the point on Origen and Epiphanius, before assessing the basic argument.

The argument from Origen's *Commentary on Romans* is a classical one in favor of the reading “Junias.” It is particularly weak, however. As Caroline Hammond Bammel's comprehensive critical edition of Rufinus' Latin translation of Origen's *Commentary* reveals, only two 12th-century manuscripts have the masculine form.²⁶ Moreover, these two belong to the same subgroup of manuscripts, as Epp accurately points out.²⁷ Ng's

²⁴ Bauckham, *Women Gospels*, 109-202; B. Witherington III, “Joanna, Apostle of the Lord—or Jailbait?,” in: *BRev* 21/2 (2005), 12-14; C. A. Clark, “Exploring the True Identity of Junia: Prominent among the Apostles,” in: *JECH* 8/3 (2018): 96-106.

²⁵ Ng later discussed the Joanna-Junia hypothesis in more detail (Ng, “Did Joanna Become Junia?”).

²⁶ C. P. Hammond Bammel (ed.), *Der Römerbriefkommentar des Origenes: Kritische Ausgabe der Übersetzung Rufins*, vol. 3 (Freiburg: Herder 1998), 836-37, here 853. The name Junia appears in four places (10.21, lines 1, 10, and 25; 10.39, line 45).

²⁷ Epp, *Junia*, 34.

statement is thus misleading (and dismissive of text critics' work) when she explains that "some scholars consider the manuscripts with the reading of *Junias* less reliable than those that render the name as *Junia* since they came later in time (12th c.)" (p. 524 – my emphasis). Of course, the scholars she alludes to (mainly Epp, judging from her footnote 27) do not base their judgment solely on the dating of the manuscripts. There are cogent reasons to think that Origen too took IOYNIAN to be a female name, and that the masculine reading occurred later at some point in the textual transmission of his work.

As to the *Index discipulorum* attributed to Epiphanius of Salamine (an alleged list of the disciples sent out by Jesus according to Luke 10:1), the case is even clearer. Ng rightly notes that the list contains the masculine duo Andronicus and Junias. What she almost omits, however, is that the list is most likely from a Pseudo-Epiphanius as it appears to be based on another list of disciples that dates from the 6th century.²⁸ Therefore, the *Index discipulorum* is most likely a 7th or 8th-century list, which makes it far from the first century and so perhaps not that reliable as to who were the 70 or 72 disciples (the exact number varies in tradition). Further, the *Index discipulorum* also contains the duo Aquilas and *Priscas* (clearly a masculinized version of the Prisca/Priscilla mentioned in Rom 16.3-4; 1 Cor 16.19; 2 Tim 4.19; Ac 18.1-5; 18.18-19, 26) and – but Ng seems to ignore this point – the name Εὐδοῦς, which is arguably a masculinized version of the woman named Evodia of Phil 4.2.²⁹ From there, I could not disagree more with Ng when she argues: "Obviously Epiphanius's information on Priscilla in his work *Index Discipulorum* was erroneous. But this does not necessarily imply the falsehood of his description of Junia" (p. 524). Actually, the presence of two other masculinized names (*Priscas* instead of Prisca and Evodios instead of Evodia) in the same list gives us excellent reasons not to trust the *Index discipulorum* on the gender of Junia(s). By far the most likely explanation is that Pseudo-Epiphanius masculinized three women, Prisca, Evodia, and Junia, to make them enter into the list of disciples. We may note in passing that nothing in Luke's Gospel specifies that the 70 or 72 disciples were all men – but this is another debate.

²⁸ As discussed by C. Guignard, "Greek Lists of the Apostles: New Findings and Open Questions," in: *ZAC* 20/3 (2016), 469-95. Ng nevertheless mentions in a footnote (without discussion) that "Bauckham and Belleville claim [...] that this work originated in the 9th century" (pages 523-24, n 26).

²⁹ I owe this point to Richard Fellows, "Early Sexist Textual Variants, and Claims That Prisca, Junia, and Julia Were Men," in: *CBQ* 84/2 (2022), 252-78, here 271.

To come to Ng’s basic argument that the Church Fathers wrongly assumed a Latin name behind IOYNIAN. Technically, this cannot be ruled out, though it would be surprising that none of them could recognise a Hebrew name (including Jerome, who knew Hebrew). The case becomes all the more difficult to sustain when we take into account that also the Coptic and, even more significantly, the Syriac manuscripts of the New Testament, have a feminine form of the name in Rom 16.7 (ἰΟΥΝΙΑ in Sahidic Coptic [ἰΟΥΓΙΑ in Bohairic], and ܝܘܢܝܐ [yūnîyâ] in Syriac).³⁰ It is scarcely conceivable that even the Syriac translators would have failed to notice that IOYNIAN reflected a Semitic name – unless we assume that the “mistake” over Junias’ gender was so well established at the time that it influenced their understanding. At this point, one may wonder whether it is not more simple to think that the Church Fathers and early translators were right to regard IOYNIAN as a feminine name!

To conclude on the Name-Gender debate, the scenario advocated by Ng proves to have few arguments in its favour. If this is not technically impossible that Ἰουνίας be the Greek rendering of the rare Hebrew name Yehunni, defending this scenario necessitates some intellectual acrobatics, namely: (1) to assume that a Hebrew name lies behind IOYNIAN, while rejecting the plausible Yeohanna hypothesis (as well as the possibility that Yehunni be a feminine name); (2) to contend that not only all the Church Fathers (including, probably, Origen), but also the translators into Coptic and Syriac, were wrong in interpreting the name. To put it another way, the Yehunni hypothesis proves likely only if we start from the assumption that a woman apostle is close to non-sense – which at this point I begin to believe is Ng’s starting assumption.

The Grammar-Syntax Debate: “Was Junia(s) an Apostle?” (p. 525-528)

In the second part of her article, Ng temporarily suspends the issue of the gender of Junia/Junias to venture into the “Grammar-Syntax debate.” She now builds on an influent theory formulated by Michael H. Burer and Daniel D. Wallace in a 2001 article, according to which the expression ἐπίσημοι ἐν τοῖς ἀποστόλοις in Rom 16.7 should not be read with the *inclusive* sense of “outstanding among the apostles,” but instead with the *exclusive*

³⁰ See Artz, “Junia oder Iunias?,” 94-95; Plisch, “Die Apostelin Junia.”

sense of “well-known to the apostles.”³¹ In short, Junia(s) and Andronicus would not be apostles themselves; they would only be *well-known* to the apostles. So even if Junia was a *woman*, she would not be an *apostle*.

The exclusive reading advocated by Wallace and Burer gained some support, mainly in evangelical and conservative scholarship.³² Its influence can also be observed in multiple modern translations (including ESV 2001, CEV, CSB, NASB 2021, and NET). In general, however, Wallace and Burer’s article has met strong criticisms. Soon after its publication, three NT scholars (Richard Bauckham in 2002, Eldon Epp in 2002, and Linda Belleville in 2005) all independently reacted and formulated strong methodological resistances against the exclusive reading suggested by Wallace and Burer.³³ Their critiques came in three points. First, they pointed out that the construction ἐν + plural dative is usually *inclusive*, meaning “in”/“among,” not “to.”³⁴ Second, they called into question the examples that Burer and Wallace provide for ἐπίσημοι ἐν + plural dative with the meaning “well-known to,” judging most of them debatable.³⁵ Belleville’s conclusion on this point is without appeal: “Burer and Wallace assume a conclusion not found in the evidence. Despite their assertions to the contrary, they fail to offer one clear biblical or extra-biblical Hellenistic example of an ‘exclusive’ sense of *episēmoi en* and a plural noun to mean ‘well known to.’”³⁶ Third, Bauckham, Belleville and Epp argued that the ancient interpretations together with the early translations rather support the inclusive reading “eminent among the apostles.” For instance, the Vulgate has *nobiles in apostolis*, “notable among the apostles.” All in all, these scholars have found a gap between the small evidence advanced by Wallace and Burer and their affirmative, assured conclusion that ἐπίσημοι ἐν τοῖς ἀποστόλοις “almost certainly” means well known to the apostles.³⁷

³¹ Burer and Wallace, “Was Junia Really an Apostle?.” Cf. also M. Burer, “ΕΠΙΣΗΜΟΙ ἘΝ ΤΟΙΣ ΑΠΟΣΤΟΛΟΙΣ in Rom 16:7.”

³² See, for example, Huttar, “Did Paul Call Andronicus an Apostle?”; P. Zell, “Exegetical Brief: Romans 16:1, 7: Phoebe, a Deacon? Junia, an Apostle?,” in: *WLQ* 111/2 (2014), 102-07; M. Harding, “Female Apostleship in Romans 16:7,” in: *DBSJ* 21 (2016), 59-86. For a comprehensive review of the reception of Burer and Wallace’s thesis, see Hamilton, “Junia as a Female Apostle,” 41-48.

³³ Bauckham, *Gospel Women*, 165-80; E. J. Epp, “Text-Critical, Exegetical, and Socio-Cultural Factors”; Belleville, “A Re-Examination.” Cf. also the discussion in Epp, *Junia*, 72-78.

³⁴ Belleville, “A Re-Examination,” 243.

³⁵ Bauckham, *Gospel Women*, 178-79; Belleville, “A Re-Examination,” 245.

³⁶ Belleville, “A Re-Examination,” 244-45.

³⁷ Burer and Wallace, “Was Junia Really an Apostle?,” 90.

In her article, Ng presents a detailed, rather balanced survey of the various opinions. She also includes the rhetorical arguments made by David Huttar in 2009 (in favour of the exclusive reading) and by Yii-Jan Lin in 2020 (in favour of the inclusive reading).³⁸ Then, she concludes as follows: “Here I will make no attempt to adjudicate between the two views. My objective is merely to point out that the common rendering of ‘prominent among the apostles’ is not unassailable truth.” (p. 526). This balanced conclusion oddly contrasts with the more affirmative tone of the abstract given on the first pages of her article: “The expression ‘notable among apostles’ *should preferably* be translated ‘esteemed by the apostles’” (p. 517 – my emphasis). But such a cautious conclusion reveals sufficient for the final purpose of Ng’s article, which is to argue that Junia cannot be taken as a *clear* precedent of female leadership for today’s church (see p. 517 and p. 532). Accordingly, the challenge is not to prove that Junia was in fact Junias or that she was not an apostle. Casting serious doubts is enough.

The Apostleship Debate: “The Role of Junia (if Female) in the First Century” (p. 528-531)

In the third part of the article, Ng finally turns to the “Apostleship debate.” In this part, she raises every possible argument to finish convincing her readership that even in the improbable situation in which “Junia” was a woman and was called ‘apostle’ (note the presence of the parenthesis “if female” in the heading of the section), then she may not have been an apostle in the full sense of the term – by which we have to understand that her ministry was “not identical with that of male apostles” (p. 531). The core of the idea is that the same term could designate a different function depending on whether it is applied to a man or a woman.³⁹ The suggestions range from the idea that Junia’s title of apostle may have been honorific to the idea that her apostolic ministry was oriented only towards women and/or exercised in a private context. This is the point that is the most difficult to argue with since one can easily concede that women probably did not have the same opportunities as men in the middle of the first century CE in the Roman Empire. Such an

³⁸ Huttar, “Did Paul Call Andronicus an Apostle?”; Lin, “Junia: An Apostle before Paul.”

³⁹ On this question, Ng opposes the principle expressed by Lynn Cohick that “the approach must be to assume, unless warranted otherwise, that a title carries the same meaning and responsibilities whether attached to a man or a woman” (L. Cohick, *Women in the World of the Earliest Christians: Illuminating Ancient Ways of Life* [Grand Rapids: Baker 2009], here 214).

idea aligns with what we know – or at least what we believe we know – about the patriarchal organisation of the Græco-Roman society. Still, we can notice a few methodological problems and shortcuts in Ng’s reasoning, that in the end make her point far less certain than she claims. The problems come from her (almost) uncritical use of the ancient sources.

First, Ng alludes to the liberality towards women’s leadership observed in Christian movements such as Montanism and Marcionism. She states (without precise references to the ancient sources): “In order to counter the female prophets and leaders in Montanism and Marcionism, a number of early Church Fathers (such as Origen, Hippolytus, Didymus the Blind, Epiphanius) appealed to Paul’s words in 1 Cor 14:34-35 and/or 1 Tim 2:12 and stated that women never publicly taught men historically and should not do so at any time.” (p. 530).

She also points out that Tertullian, even after he adhered to Montanism, still “stated that a female prophet who often saw visions in his church would only relate to the church leaders in private after the service concerning what she actually saw.”⁴⁰ (p. 530) She then goes on explaining (again without mentioning the exact references she has in mind) that: “Certain church manuals or orders restricted the sphere of ministry of women (including widows, virgins, and deacons), such as serving women alone, or leaving to male leaders the responsibility of teaching deeper doctrine.” (p. 530)

These general remarks are grounded. That women were restricted or at the very least that they should be restricted to some spheres of activity (the private sphere) is indeed a common idea in patristic literature and church orders. For the church orders, we may think for instance of the *Didascalia apostolorum* (3rd century), which draws a double distinction between the roles attributed to male and female deacons: first, the female deacons should orient their activities towards women; second, some acts of the baptism ritual (for example, the pronouncement of the divine names on the water) ought to be done by a man.⁴¹ The problem here is that Ng seems to trust a little bit too much such doctrinal texts to inform

⁴⁰ This is an allusion to Tertullian, *De anima* 9.4.

⁴¹ *Didascalia*, chapter XVI; on baptism by women, cf. also chapter XV (for an English translation, see A. Stewart-Sykes, *The Didascalia Apostolorum: An English Version with Introduction and Annotation* [Turnhout: Brepols 2009]).

us about the concrete situation of Junia in the middle of the first century CE. Here, she seems to overlook two crucial points.

First, we should take into account the nature of the sources we use. In the case of the texts Ng refers to, they are to a large extent prescriptive. As to women's leadership and ministries, they thus depict what their authors believed should be. For instance, when Epiphanius states that "never and nowhere women were priests,"⁴² his narrative aligns with what he believes should have been and should forever be in the "Great Church." It is clear, however, that his statement cannot be taken as a faithful description of practices of his time or the earlier times, since we have in fact multiple attestations of women priests in the early Church. This is true for movements that came to be deemed "heretical" by the ecclesiastical authorities (for example, Priscillianism [a subgroup of Montanism] and Collyridianism, as Epiphanius himself describes⁴³), but close attention to ancient sources reveals that (at least a few) women priests have also been active within "orthodox" circles. For instance, one may think of the epitaphs of Ammion (Phrygia, late second century),⁴⁴ Leta (Bruttium, fourth or fifth century),⁴⁵ and Kale (Sicily, fourth or fifth century),⁴⁶ or of the label of the mummy Artemidora (Egypt, second or third century),⁴⁷ or of bishop Firmilien's complaint that a woman had dared to sacrifice and baptise in a Christian community in Cappadocia (mid-third century),⁴⁸ or of Pope Gelasius's letter to bishops in south Italy in which he reports that he had heard of women that are "encouraged [*firmentur*] to serve at the sacred altars and to perform all the other tasks that are assigned only to the service of men" in

⁴² Epiphanius, *Panarion* 79.2.

⁴³ Epiphanius, *Panarion* 49.1 (on Priscillianism); 79.1 (Collyridianism).

⁴⁴ A. Körte, *Inscriptiones Bureschianae* (Greifswald: Abel 1902): 31, no 55. The scholarly discussion is still open as to whether the priest Ammion belonged to the Montanist movement: see U. E. Eisen, *Women Officeholders in Early Christianity: Epigraphical and Literary Studies* (transl. L. M. Maloney; Collegeville: Liturgical / Michael Glazier 2000 [German original: *Amtsträgerinnen im frühen Christentum*, 1996]), 116-123; K. Madigan and C. Osiek, *Ordained Women in the Early Church: A Documentary History* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press 2005), 170; cf. also W. Tabbernee, "Women Office Holders in Montanism," in: J. E. Taylor and Ilaria L. E. Ramelli (eds.), *Patterns of Women's Leadership in Early Christianity* (Oxford: Oxford University Press 2021), 151-79.

⁴⁵ CIL X.8079. On Leta as a priest, see G. Otranto, "Note sul sacerdozio femminile nell'antichità in margine a una testimonianza di Gelasio I," in: *Vetera Christianorum* 19/2 (1982), 341-60; Eisen, *Women Officeholders*, 131; Madigan and Osiek, *Ordained Women*, 195.

⁴⁶ On the inscription of Kale, see Eisen, *Women Officeholders*, 128-129.

⁴⁷ For the first edition, see F. Baratte et B. Boyaval, "Catalogue des étiquettes de momies du Musée du Louvre (C.E.M.L.): textes grecs, 4ème partie," in: *CRIPPEL* 5 (1979), 237-39, here 264. On Artemidora as a priest, see Eisen, *Women Officeholders*, 126-28; cf. Madigan et Osiek, *Ordained Women*, 170.

⁴⁸ Cyprien, *Correspondance*, Letter 75.10.1-5. For a discussion of the passage, see Madigan and Osiek, *Ordained Women*, 181-82.

their communities (late 5th century),⁴⁹ or of the frescoes of the priests (or bishops?) Cerula and Bitinia in the catacombs of San Genarro in Naples (late 5th century-early 6th century).⁵⁰ To keep it short: there were some discrepancies between the theories expressed by the Church Fathers and church orders on the one hand, and on the other hand the realities on the ground.

Second, one can notice how far the texts Ng refers to are temporally quite distant from Paul, Andronicus and Junia's time. Tertullian wrote 150 years after Paul, Origen and Hippolytus almost 200 years after Paul, Didym the Blind 300 years after Paul, and Epiphanius around 350 years after Paul. As to the church orders Ng seems to allude (without making clear which texts exactly she has in mind), they are also all quite distant from Paul: first part of the third century for the *Didascalia*, late fourth century for the *Constitutiones apostolorum* and the *Canons of the Concile of Nimes*. So even assuming that the Church Fathers and the church orders would offer a reliable depiction of the practices of their time – rather than a more prescriptive view as suggested above – it remains that both opinions and practices may have evolved a lot between Jesus and Paul's time (mid-first century) and the time these texts were written, notwithstanding the variations according to geography and the interactions with other religious groups of the same region. That women were (at least theoretically) not allowed to do this or that in Carthage in the early third century or in Alexandria in the middle of the fourth century does not necessarily imply they some women may not have done – and even be allowed to do – the exact same thing in the middle of the first century in Palestine or Rome.

Early Christianity was not a monolithic movement. The few elements evoked above are enough to show that there was not something like an all-unified and coherent set of beliefs and practices with regard to women's ministries. Instead, Christians appear to have been divided about this question from an early date, if not from the very beginning. So one cannot simply assume that women's leadership never existed or that women were

⁴⁹ Gelasius, "Decretal to the bishops of Lucania, Bruttium, and Sicily" (= Letter 14). The translation above reproduces that by Madigan and Osiek, *Ordained Women*, 186. For a detailed discussion on this passage, see G. Otranto, "Note sul sacerdozio femminile"; cf. also Madigan et Osiek, *Ordained Women*, 186-88.

⁵⁰ On these frescoes, restored from 2009 to 2011, see A. Kateusz, *Mary and Early Christian Women: Hidden Leadership* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan 2019): 158-61; A. Kateusz et L. Badini Confalonieri, "Women Church Leaders in and around Fifth-Century Rome," in Taylor and Ramelli (eds.), *Patterns of Women's Leadership*, 253-58.

subordinated to men everywhere and anytime. This image simply does not fit with the evidence at hand. Returning to the first century, I do not know how liberal Paul himself was on men-women relationships. In any case, given the number of women that are mentioned in the final salutations of the Epistle to the Romans (Rom 16) and the qualifiers associated with them,⁵¹ it is all the more plausible that the members of the Christian Roman community to which Paul wrote (and Paul himself, up to a certain extent) were on the liberal' side of the spectrum.

For sure, it might be that Junia's apostolic ministry faced resistance from some of her contemporaries, who thought that she should better not teach, not baptise, and perhaps stay at home. It might be that some men (and women) did not wish to listen to her preaching and disregarded her words (like the eleven and the others reacted when women first announced the resurrection, according to Lk 24.9-11, cf. also Mk 16.9-11), or considered her merely as an assistant of Andronicus. It is also possible that Junia oriented her work merely towards women. And so what, to paraphrase Ng? It seems to me that there is a gap between acknowledging this and concluding that Junia was not a "real" or "full" apostle. But probably it all depends on what we consider to be the "seal of apostleship" (to borrow from Paul's expression in 1 Cor 9.2) and who exactly is able to evaluate whether someone is legitimate or not to exercise a "full" apostolic ministry (God? Jesus? Paul? Peter? Other apostles? The Church Fathers? Modern scholars?). As to the more practical question of the implications of the Junia case for today's church, however, I will not enter into debate with Ng on this point. My own theological perspective is far too distant from hers, as I do not think we should take Paul's or the Church Fathers' views on women-men relationships as gospel, nor do I think that the ecclesiastical organization of the first Christians communities ought to serve as the ultimate, definitive model for today's practices.

⁵¹ On the many women mentioned in Romans 16, see, for example, the study by S. Mathews, *Women in the Greetings of Romans 16.1-16: A Study of Mutuality and Women's Ministry in the Letter to the Romans* (London / New York: Bloomsbury T&T Clark 2013).

The Core of the Problem: The Negation of the Androcentric Bias in the History of Interpretation

Already in her introduction, Ng announced that she has strong doubts about the alleged “androcentric bias” that most scholars today believe has created the Junia(s) debate from scratch (p. 518-19). Accordingly, one of the announced aims of her article is to “address the charge of androcentrism” (p. 519). From this point, one would expect to find somewhere in the article some discussion to explain the history of the Junia/Junias debate in a different light. For instance, I would have been willing to find at least a hypothesis as to what, if not androcentrism, led to such a success of the contracted-name theory (Ἰουνιάς as a hypocoristic of *Iunianus*) in the 19th and 20th centuries. Or what, if not some sort of androcentric conceptions, may have led NA editors to modify Ἰουνιᾶν into Ἰουνίαν in 1927, resulting in a spelling that is supported by exactly *zero* manuscript?!

However, reading Ng’s article reveals frustrating as no discussion of these issues is offered. Contrary to her announced aim, the author does not at all *address* these issues. It seems that she simply decides to work with what we could call an “axiom of unsuspection” that consists of suspending the very possibility that androcentrism may have played any role at some points in the history of interpretation of Rom 16.7. This rather naive starting point is pretty convenient for Ng’s case, as this permits her, for instance, to give credit to the (Pseudo-)Epiphanius’ *Index discipulorum* with regard to the masculine gender of Junias – even if this list also contains masculinized forms of both Prisca (Priscas) and Evodia (Evodios). But to refute the theory that Junia came to be masculinised in modern scholarship and translations due to an androcentric bias, one has to do more than proposing an alternative scenario (Junias as a Hellenized form of the Hebrew name Yehunni) that is convincing only if we assume in the first place that a woman apostle is too unlikely! All in all, Ng’s article proves to be a perfect illustration of the androcentric bias of which she seeks to rebut the existence.

Further, it is worth noting that even if the Yehunni hypothesis formulated by Wolters or the exclusive reading advocated by Burrer and Wallace proved to be correct in the end, it would still remain that the best explanation as to why the masculine Junia has come to prevail in modern receptions is an *androcentric bias* (where androcentrism is understood as a vision of the world in which power and spiritual authority are spontaneously associated

with men). Until a better explanation is proposed – once again, Ng does *not* offer a shred of an alternative explanation – the best option is to recognise that a serious androcentric bias was at work in 19th- and 20th-century NT scholarship. Saying this is not “calumny,” contrary to Ng’s suggestion (p. 532). Neither is it an intrinsic “feminist” point of view. It is a fair conclusion based on a careful, detailed, critical analysis of the evidence that is on the table.⁵²

Conclusion

The article by Ng is cleverly constructed (with a three-stage “funnel” *dispositio*) and does demonstrate a good general knowledge of the scholarly debate on the Junia case. Readers who are unfamiliar with the debate at hand and with the history of women in early Christianity might easily conclude that there remain strong doubts as to the gender, title, and role of Junia(s). Once it has been critically assessed and its global rhetorical strategy exposed, however, her argumentation appears far less convincing.

Throughout her article, Ng relies on the rhetorical effect of *accumulatio* by picking up and insisting on every element that might cast some doubt about the case for Junia as a woman apostle. She does so regardless of how problematic some arguments are and notwithstanding the mass of arguments for the opposite view. At some points, Ng even omits crucial pieces of information or lets them in footnotes: she does not mention that early translations in Coptic and Syriac support the feminine; she omits to specify that the Hebrew name Yehunni might also be feminine (according to Al Wolter’s himself); she does not provide sufficient background about the manuscripts of Origen’s *Commentary on Romans*; she does not seriously consider the hypothesis that Junia could be the Latin-Greek rendering of Yeohanna; etc. This is a typical case of how confirmation bias works.

All in all, it appears that Ng is just embroidering around the same (and sole) traditional argument that the existence of a woman apostle is unlikely. Such an argument from “common-sense” was certainly apt to convince both scholars and the broad public for a while. However, in view of the development of research on the history of women over the

⁵² To be perfectly clear: I do not think that NT scholars were all misogynistic or especially sexist when the masculine reading Junias took importance (in this sense, contrary to Ng, I would not speak of a “charge of androcentrism”). The Junia case only illustrates how NT scholars and translators were (and still are, for some of them) used to see the past through a male-centred perspective.

last fifty years, which has found numerous examples of women leadership in Antiquity, including in early Christianity,⁵³ the simple idea “it is unlikely that a woman can be an apostle” no longer holds as a self-evident reading grid in the 2020s. Someone would finally need to justify this assumption.

⁵³ I am thinking, for example, of the monographs by Elisabeth Schüssler Fiorenza (*In Memory of Her. A Feminist Theological Reconstruction of Christian Origins* [London: SCM 1983]), Karen Jo Torjesen (*When Women Were Priests: Women’s Leadership in the Early Church and the Scandal of Their Subordination in the Rise of Christianity* [San Francisco: Harper 1995]), Ute Eisen (*Women Officeholders*), Lynn Cohick, *Women in the World of the Earliest Christians*, Mary Schaefer (*Women in Pastoral Office: The Story of Santa Prassede, Rome* [New York: Oxford University Press 2013]), Christine Schenk (*Crispina and her Sisters: Women and Authority in Early Christianity* [Minneapolis: Fortress Press 2017]), and Ally Kateusz (*Mary and Early Christian Women*); of the “documentary history” by Kevin Madigan and Carolin Osiek (*Ordained Women in the Early Church*); or the recent edited volume by Joan E. Taylor and Ilaria Ramelli (*Patterns of Women’s Leadership*).